

Supporting Information for

Deciphering the Distribution and Types of Multicopper Oxidases in Basidiomycota Fungi

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Legends for Dataset S1

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Other supporting materials for this manuscript include the following:

Dataset S1

Supplementary Files 1 - 4

Table S1. MCO enzymes present in the 107 analyzed species of Basidiomycota fungi distributed in the following groups: LAC, NLAC, NMCO, NLF, FOX, LAC-FOX, Fungal pigment MCO and AO. The color background of each fungal species corresponds to their taxonomic position. 'ABBR. JGI' indicates the abbreviation of each species according to the DOE JGI MycoCosm Portal nomenclature and 'GENOME' the species with the culture collection reference. 'Selected sequences' encompasses the complete set of 1217 MCO sequences that have been chosen for the study. The column labelled '**' comprises MCO sequences that exceptionally represent a classification challenge in any of the 8 defined MCO groups. 'Discarded sequences' indicates the number of partial sequences that did not meet the criterion followed in the initial filtering process, and 'Initial sequences' denotes the number of sequences that were initially downloaded for consideration in the study.

TAXONOMY	ABBR. JGI	GENOME	SELECTED SEQUENCES									DISCARDED SEQUENCES	INITIAL SEQUENCES		
			LACCASE-TYPE MCO				LAC FOX	FOX	PIGMENT MCO	AO	**			TOTAL	
			LAC	NLAC	NMCO	NLF									
1	Agaricales	Hypsu1	Hypholoma sublateritium v1.0	9	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	12	1	13
2	Agaricales	Phocou1	Pholiota conissans CIRM-BRFM674 v1.0	8	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	11	0	11
3	Agaricales	Phoain1	Pholiota alnicola AH 47727 v1.0	8	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	10	2	12
4	Agaricales	Hebcy2	Hebeloma cylindrosporum h7 v2.0	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	3	1	4
5	Agaricales	Psiser1	Psilocybe serbica v1.0	13	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	15	2	17
6	Agaricales	Agpdp1	Agrocybe pediades AH40210 v1.0	11	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	13	0	13
7	Agaricales	Gymjun1	Gymnopilus junonius AH 44721 v1.0	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	4	2	6
8	Agaricales	Galma1	Galerina marginata v1.0	7	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	9	0	9
9	Agaricales	Crevar1	Crepidotus variabilis CBS 506.95 v1	5	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	6	1	7
10	Agaricales	Panpap1	Panaeolus papilionaceus CIRM-BRFM 715 v1.0	6	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	9	1	10
11	Agaricales	Crafun1	Crassisporium funariophilum CBS 144457 v1.0	5	-	-	3	-	1	-	-	-	9	0	9
12	Agaricales	Corg3	Cortinariopsis glaucopus AT 2004 276 v2.0	5	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	8	0	8
13	Agaricales	Copci_AmutBmut1	Coprinopsis cinerea AmutBmut pab1-1 v1.0	14	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	16	1	17
14	Agaricales	Copmic2	Coprinellus micaceus FP101781 v2.0	14	-	-	3	-	1	-	-	-	18	1	19
15	Agaricales	Lacam2	Laccaria amethystina LaAM-08-1 v2.0	6	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	8	1	9
16	Agaricales	Cyast2	Cyathus striatus AH40144 v1.0	9	1	1	-	-	3	-	-	-	14	0	14
17	Agaricales	Crula1	Crucibulum laeve CBS 166.37 v1.0	9	2	2	2	-	1	-	-	-	16	1	17
18	Agaricales	Macfu1	Macrolepiota fuliginosa v1.0	16	4	5	-	-	1	-	-	-	26	12	38
19	Agaricales	Leugon1	Leucoagaricus gongylophorus AB2 v1.0	6	1	2	-	-	1	-	-	-	10	0	10
20	Agaricales	Agabi_varbisH97_2	Agaricus bisporus var bisporus (H97) v2.0	10	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	13	0	13
21	Agaricales	Trima3	Tricholoma matsutake 945 v3.0	13	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	14	2	16
22	Agaricales	Lyoot1	Lyophyllum atratum CBS 144462 v1.0	16	2	4	2	-	1	-	-	-	25	0	25
23	Agaricales	Cligb1	Clitocybe gibba IJFM A808 v1.0	2	3	6	-	-	1	-	-	-	12	3	15
24	Agaricales	Volvo1	Volvariella volvacea V23	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	0	11
25	Agaricales	Plucer1	Pluteus cervinus NL-1719 v1.0	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	2	11
26	Agaricales	Rhobut1_1	Rhodocollybia butyracea AH40177 v1.0	16	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	19	1	20
27	Agaricales	Lened1	Lentinula edodes NBRC 111202	9	1	4	-	1	1	-	-	-	16	0	16
28	Agaricales	Gyman1	Gymnopus androsaceus JB14 v1.0	21	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	24	7	31
29	Agaricales	Gymlu1	Gymnopus luxurians v1.0	9	2	5	-	1	2	-	-	-	19	0	19
30	Agaricales	Ompol1	Omphalotus olearius	5	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	8	0	8
31	Agaricales	Denbi1	Dendrothele bispora CBS 962.96 v1.0	15	6	3	4	4	3	-	-	-	35	13	48
32	Agaricales	Marfi1	Marasmius fiardii PR-910 v1.0	14	2	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	20	4	24
33	Agaricales	Oudmuc1	Oudemansiella mucida CBS558.79 v1.0	8	2	-	2	1	2	1	-	-	16	1	17
34	Agaricales	Hymrad1	Hymenopellis radicata UFM160 v1.0	6	2	1	4	1	4	1	-	-	19	4	23
35	Agaricales	Cyto1	Cylindrobasidium torrendii FP15055 v1.0	3	-	-	-	1	-	4	-	-	8	0	8
36	Agaricales	Armg1	Armillaria gallica 21-2 v1.0	15	3	3	1	-	2	1	-	-	25	1	26
37	Agaricales	Mycga1	Mycena galopus ATCC-62051 v1.0	17	2	6	-	3	5	-	-	-	33	6	39
38	Agaricales	Schco3	Schizophyllum commune H4-8 v3.0	2	-	-	-	1	-	2	1	-	6	0	6
39	Agaricales	Auramp1	Auriculariopsis ampla NL-1724 v1.0	4	-	-	-	-	-	2	2	-	9	0	9
40	Agaricales	Fishe1	Fistulina hepatica v1.0	3	-	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	6	0	6
41	Agaricales	Pleery1	Pleurotus eryngii ATCC 90797 v1.0	9	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	11	0	11
42	Agaricales	PleosPC15_2	Pleurotus ostreatus PC15 v2.0	10	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	12	0	12
43	Boletales	Paxam1	Paxillus ammoniavirescens Pou09.2 v1.0	13	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	15	1	16
44	Boletales	Boled5	Boletus edulis BED1 v4.0	7	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	10	0	10
45	Boletales	Hydpi2	Hydnomerulius pinastri v2.0	9	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	11	0	11
46	Boletales	Scloi1	Scleroderma citrinum Foug A v1.0	9	-	-	-	0	1	-	-	-	10	1	11
47	Boletales	Pismi2	Pisolithus microcarpus 441 v2.0	7	-	-	-	0	1	-	-	-	8	1	9
48	Boletales	Sulamp1	Suillus ampilporus FC55 v1.0	12	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	14	0	14
49	Boletales	Conpu1	Coniophora puteana v1.0	6	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	8	0	8
50	Boletales	SeriaS7_3_2	Serpula lacrymans S7.3 v2.0	4	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	6	0	6
51	Atheliales	Fibsp1	Fibulorhizoctonia sp. CBS 109695 v1.0	30	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	33	4	37
52	Atheliales	Plicr1	Piloderma coeruleum F 1598 v1.0	11	-	-	-	4	3	-	2	-	20	2	22
53	Amylocorticiales	Plicr1	Plicaturopsis crispa v1.0	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	0	6
54	Polyporales	PostpiRSB12_1	Postia placenta MAD-698-R-SB12 v1.0	2	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	4	0	4
55	Polyporales	Fibra1	Fibroporia radiculosa TFFH 294	2	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	4	0	4
56	Polyporales	Wolco1	Wolfiporia cocos MD-104 SS10 v1.0	3	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	5	0	5
57	Polyporales	Fomros1	Rhodofomes roseus CIRM-BRFM 1785 v1.0	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	4
58	Polyporales	Pipbet1_1	Fomitopsis betulina CIRM-BRFM 1772 v1.1	2	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	4	0	4
59	Polyporales	Cersu1	Ceriporiopsis (Gelatorporia) subvermispora B	7	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	9	0	9
60	Polyporales	Obbri1	Obba rivulosa 3A-2 v1.0	8	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	10	0	10
61	Polyporales	Dicsqu18370_1	Dichomitus squalens OM18370.1 v1.0	11	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	13	1	14
62	Polyporales	Gansp1	Ganoderma sp. 10597 SS1 v1.0	15	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	17	1	18
63	Polyporales	Lent7_1	Lentinus tigrinus ALCF2SS1-7 v1.0	9	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	11	0	11
64	Polyporales	Polbr1	Polyporus brumalis BRFM 1820 v1.0	9	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	11	0	11
65	Polyporales	Earsca1	Earliella scabra CIRM-BRFM 1817 v1.0	8	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	10	0	10
66	Polyporales	Pyccl1	Pycnoporus cinnabarinus CIRM-BRFM 137 v1.0	5	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	7	0	7
67	Polyporales	Tramen1	Leiotrametes menziesii CIRM-BRFM 1781 v1.0	4	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	6	0	6
68	Polyporales	Trave1	Trametes versicolor v1.0	7	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	10	0	10
69	Polyporales	Phchr2	Phanerochaete chrysosporium RP-78 v2.2	-	-	-	-	4	1	-	-	-	5	0	5
70	Polyporales	Phlgi1	Phlebiopsis gigantea v1.0	-	-	-	-	4	1	-	-	-	5	1	6
71	Polyporales	Bjead1_1	Bjerkandera adusta v1.0	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	2	0	2
72	Polyporales	Hydfim1	Hydnopolyporus fimbriatus CBS384.51 v1.0	-	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	3	0	3
73	Polyporales	Trace1	Trametes coccinea CIRM-BRFM 1824 v1.0	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	2	0	2
74	Polyporales	Phlrad1	Phlebia radiata Fr. (isolate 79, FBCC0043)	5	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	7	0	7
75	Polyporales	Panru1	Panus rudis PR-1116 ss-1 v1.0	6	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	9	0	9
76	Polyporales	Abobie1	Abortiporus biennis CIRM-BRFM1778 v1.0	10	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	12	0	12
77	Telephorales	Theter1	Thelephora terrestris UH-T-Lm1 v1.0	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	0	2
78	Gloeophyllales	Glotr1_1	Gloeophyllum trabeum v1.0	4	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	5	0	5
79	Gloeophyllales	Neole1	Neolentinus lepideus v1.0	4	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	5	0	5
80	Russulales	Lacqui1	Lactarius quietus S23C v1.0	11	-	-	-	5	1	-	-	-	17	6	23
81	Russulales	Rusoch1	Russula ochroleuca Pfliba v1.0	10	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	12	1	13
82	Russulales	Lopni1	Peniophora sp. CONTA v1.0	19	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	21	2	23
83	Russulales	Hetan2	Heterobasidium annosum v2.0	11	1	2	-	2	1	-	-	-	18	1	19
84	Russulales	Stehi1	Stereum hirsutum FP-91666 SS1 v1.0	11	1	3	-	2	2	-	1	-	20	2	22
85	Russulales	Densp1	Dentipellis sp. KUC8613 v1.0	3	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	5	1	6
86	Hymenochaetales	Schpa1	Schizophora paradoxa KUC8140 v1.0	5	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	6	0	6
87	Hymenochaetales	Fomme1	Fomitiporia mediterranea v1.0	10	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	11	1	12
88	Hymenochaetales	Rigmic1	Rigidoporus microporus ED310 v1.	5	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	7	0	7
89	Hymenochaetales	Ricme1	Rickenella mellea v1.0 (SZMC22713)	7	1	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	10	0	10
90	* Phallomycetidae	Ramac1	Ramaria rubella (R. acris) UT-36052-T v1.0	-	5	1	4	2	1	-	1	1	15	2	17
91	* Phallomycetidae	Gaumor1_1	Gautieria morcheliformis GMNE.BST v1.0	-	2	-	-	9	-	1	-	-	12	2	14
92	* Phallomycetidae	Hyssto1	Hysterangium stoloniferum HS.BST v1.0	-	1	-	-	13	2	1	-	-	18	4	22
93	* Phallomycetidae	Sphst1	Sphaerobolus stellatus v1.0	-	-	-	-	14	2	1	-	1	18	16	34
94	Auriculariales	Aurde3_1	Auricularia subglabra v2.0	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	-	5	9	3	12
95	Auriculariales	Exigi1	Exidia glandulosa v1.0	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	-	6	9	2	11
96	Sebacinales	Pirin1	Piriformospora indica DSM 11827 from MPI	-	-	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	3	0	3
97	Sebacinales	Sebbe1	Sebacina vermifera MAFF 305830 v1.0	-	-	-	-	5	-	1	-	-	6	0	6
98	Cantharellales	Rhiso1	Rhizoctonia solani AG-1 IB	-	-	-	-	9	3	1	7	-	20	10	30
99	Cantharellales	CerAG1	Ceratobasidium sp. anastomosis group t; DN8442 v1.0	-	-	-	-	6	5	1	4	-	16	4	20
100	Dacrymycetes	Calvi1	Calocera viscosa v1.0	-	-	-	-	2	2	-	-	3	7	1	8
101	Dacrymycetes	Dacsp1	Dacryopinax primgonitius DJM 731 SSP1 v1.0	-	-	-	-	2	2	-	-	1	5	1	6
102	Tremellomyces	Cryne_H99_1	Cryptococcus neoformans var. grubii H99	-	-	-	-	2	3	-	-	-	5	0	5
103	Tremellomyces	Trias8904	Trichosporon asahii var. asahii CBS 8904	-	-	-	-	5	1	-	-	-	6	0	6
104	* Pucciniomycotina	Melame1	Melampsora americana R15-033-03 v1.0	-	-	-	-	9	1	-	5	-	15	0	15
104	*														

Table S2. Representative members of each MCO group used as probes for each cluster in the second phylogenetic analysis.

MCO	Source (JGI ref.; name)	PDB	Reference
LAC	<i>Pycnoporus cinnabarinus</i> (JGI Pycci1-8672)	2XYB	Camarero et al., 2012
	<i>Trametes versicolor</i> (JGI Trave1-138261)	1KYA	Bertrand et al., 2002
NLAC	<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> (JGI PleosPC15_2-1067328; POXA3)		Giardina et al., 2007
NMCO	<i>Leucoagaricus gongylophorus</i> (JGI Leugon1-1403257; pseudolaccase)		Taprab et al., 2005
NLF	<i>Coprinopsis cinerea</i> (JGI Copci-AmutBmut1-501548; lcc17)		Kilaru et al., 2006
FOX	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (FET3)	1ZPU	Taylor et al., 2005
LACFOX	<i>Phanerochaete chrysosporium</i> (MCO1)		Larrondo et al., 2003
MCO pigment	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> (abr2)		Sugareva et al., 2006
AO	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i> var. <i>melopepo</i>	1AOZ	Messerschmidt et al., 1992

	ABBR_JGI	GENOME_JGI	NLAC	NMCO	SS
1	Hypsu1	Hypholoma sublateritium v1.0	-	-	-
2	Phoco1	Pholiota conissans CIRM-BRFM674 v1.0	-	-	-
3	Phoaln1	Pholiota alnicola AH 47727 v1.0	-	-	-
4	Hebcy2	Hebeloma cylindrosporum h7 v2.0	-	-	-
5	Psiser1	Psilocybe serbica v1.0	-	-	-
6	Agpdp1	Agrocybe pediades AH40210 v1.0	-	-	-
7	Gymjun1	Gymnopilus junonius AH 44721 v1.0	-	-	-
8	Galma1	Galerina marginata v1.0	-	-	-
9	Crevar1	Crepidotus variabilis CBS 506.95 v1	-	-	-
10	Panpap1	Panaeolus papilionaceus CIRM-BRFM 715 v1.0	-	-	-
11	Crafun1	Crassisporium funariophilum CBS 144457 v1.0	-	-	-
12	Corgl3	Cortinarius glaucopus AT 2004 276 v2.0	-	-	-
13	Copci_AmutBmut1	Coprinopsis cinerea AmutBmut.pab1-1 v1.0	-	-	-
14	Copmic2	Coprinellus micaceus FP101781 v2.0	-	-	-
15	Lacam2	Laccaria amethystina LaAM-08-1 v2.0	-	-	-
16	Cyast2	Cyathus striatus AH40144 v1.0	1	1	1
17	Crula1	Crucibulum laeve CBS 166.37 v1.0	2	2	1
18	Macfu1	Macrospora fuliginosa v1.0	4	5	1
19	Leugon1	Leucoagaricus gonygophorus AB2 v1.0	1	2	1
20	Agabi_varbisH97_2	Agaricus bisporus var bisporus (H97) v2.0	2	-	1
21	Trim3	Tricholoma matsutake 945 v3.0	-	-	-
22	Lyofa1	Lyophyllum atratum CBS 144462 v1.0	2	4	1
23	Cligb1	Clitocybe gibba IJFM A808 v1.0	3	6	1
24	Volvo1	Volvariella volvacea V23	-	-	-
25	Plucer1	Pluteus cervinus NL-1719 v1.0	-	-	-
26	Rhobut1_1	Rhodocollybia butyracea AH40177 v1.0	-	-	2
27	Lened1	Lentinula edodes NBRC 111202	1	4	2
28	Gyman1	Gymnopus androsaceus JB14 v1.0	-	-	-
29	Gymlu1	Gymnopus luxurians v1.0	2	5	1
30	Ompol1	Omphalotus olearius	-	-	-
31	Denbi1	Dendrothele bispora CBS 962.96 v1.0	6	3	2
32	Marf1	Marasmius fiardii PR-910 v1.0	2	2	1
33	Oudmuc1	Oudemansiella mucida CBS558.79 v1.0	2	-	1
34	Hymrad1	Hymenopellis radicata IJFM160 v1.0	2	1	1
35	Cyto1	Cylindrobasidium torrendii FP15055 v1.0	-	-	-
36	Arnga1	Armillaria gallica 21-2 v1.0	3	3	1
37	Mycga1	Mycena galopus ATCC-62051 v1.0	2	6	4
38	Schco3	Schizophyllum commune H4-8 v3.0	-	-	-
39	Auramp1	Auriculariopsis ampla NL-1724 v1.0	-	-	-
40	Fishe1	Fistulina hepatica v1.0	-	-	-
41	Pleery1	Pleurotus eryngii ATCC 90797 v1.0	1	-	2
42	PleosPC15_2	Pleurotus ostreatus PC15 v2.0	1	-	2
43	Paxam1	Paxillus ammoniavirescens Pou09.2 v1.0	-	-	-
44	Boled5	Boletus edulis BED1 v4.0	-	-	-
45	Hydpl2	Hydnum erigeron pinastri v2.0	-	-	-
46	Scici1	Scleroderma citrinum Foug A v1.0	-	-	-
47	Pisim2	Pisolithus microcarpus 441 v2.0	-	-	-
48	Suiamp1	Suillus ampliporus FC55 v1.0	-	-	-
49	Conpu1	Coniophora puteana v1.0	-	-	-
50	SerlaS7_3_2	Serpula lacrymans S7.3 v2.0	-	-	-
51	Fibsp1	Fibulorhizoctonia sp. CBS 109695 v1.0	-	-	-
52	Pilcr1	Piloderma croceum F 1598 v1.0	-	-	-
53	Pilcr1	Plicaturopsis crispa v1.0	-	-	-
54	PosplRSB12_1	Postia placenta MAD-698-R-SB12 v1.0	-	-	-
55	Fibra1	Fibroporia radiculosa TFFH 294	-	-	-
56	Wolco1	Wolfiporia cocos MD-104 SS10 v1.0	-	-	-
57	Fomos1	Rhodofomes roseus CIRM-BRFM 1785 v1.0	-	-	-
58	Pipbet1_1	Fomitopsis betulina CIRM-BRFM 1772 v1.1	-	-	-
59	Cersu1	Ceriporiopsis (Gelatorporia) subvermispora B	-	-	-
60	Obbr1	Obba rivulosa 3A-2 v1.0	-	-	-
61	Dicsqu18370_1	Dichomitulus squelens OM18370.1 v1.0	-	-	-
62	Gansp1	Ganoderma sp. 10597 SS1 v1.0	-	-	-
63	LentU7_1	Lentinus tigrinus ALCF25S1-7 v1.0	-	-	-
64	Polbr1	Polyporus brumalis BRFM 1820 v1.0	-	-	-
65	Earsca1	Earliella scabrosa CIRM-BRFM 1817 v1.0	-	-	-
66	Pycoci1	Pycnoporus cinnabarinus CIRM-BRFM 137 v1.0	-	-	-
67	Tramen1	Leiotrametes menziesii CIRM-BRFM 1781 v1.0	-	-	-
68	Trave1	Trametes versicolor v1.0	-	-	-
69	Phchr2	Phanerochaete chrysosporium RP-78 v2.2	-	-	-
70	Phigi1	Phlebiopsis gigantea v1.0	-	-	-
71	Bjead1_1	Bjerkandera adusta v1.0	-	-	-
72	Hydfim1	Hydnopolyporus fimbriatus CBS384.51 v1.0	-	-	-
73	Trace1	Trametopsis cervina CIRM-BRFM 1824 v1.0	-	-	-
74	Phlrad1	Phlebia radiata Fr. (isolate 79, FBCC0043)	-	-	-
75	Panru1	Panus rudis PR-1116 ss-1 v1.0	-	-	-
76	Abobie1	Abortiporus biennis CIRM-BRFM1778 v1.0	-	-	-
77	Theter1	Thelephora terrestris UH-Tt-Lm1 v1.0	-	-	-
78	Glotr1_1	Gloeophyllum trabeum v1.0	-	-	-
79	Neole1	Neolentinus lepideus v1.0	-	-	-
80	Lacqui1	Lactarius quietus S23C v1.0	-	-	-
81	Rusoch1	Russula ochroleuca Pfliba v1.0	-	-	-
82	Lopni1	Peniophora sp. CONTA v1.0	-	-	-
83	Hetan2	Heterobasidium annosum v2.0	1	2	2
84	Stehi1	Stereum hirsutum FP-91666 SS1 v1.0	1	3	1
85	Densp1	Dentipellis sp. KUC8613 v1.0	-	-	-
86	Schpa1	Schizophora paradoxa KUC8140 v1.0	-	-	-
87	Fomme1	Fomitiporia mediterranea v1.0	-	-	1
88	Rigmic1	Rigidoporus microporus ED310 v1.	-	-	-
89	Ricmel1	Rickenella mellea v1.0 (SZMC22713)	1	-	1
90	Ramac1	Ramaria rubella (R. acris) UT-36052-T v1.0	5	1	-
91	Gaamor1_1	Gautieria morchelliformis GMNE BST v1.0	2	-	-
92	Hyssto1	Hysterangium stoloniferum HS.BST v1.0	1	-	-
93	Sphst1	Sphaerobolus stellatus v1.0	-	-	-
94	Aurde3_1	Auricularia subglabra v2.0	-	-	-
95	Exigl1	Exidia glandulosa v1.0	-	-	-
96	Pirin1	Piriformospora indica DSM 11827 from MPI	-	-	-
97	Sebbe1	Sebacina vermifera MAFF 305830 v1.0	-	-	-
98	Rhiso1	Rhizoctonia solani AG-1 B	-	-	-
99	CerAGI	Ceratobasidium sp. anastomosis group t: DN8442 v1.0	-	-	-
100	Calv1	Calocera viscosa v1.0	-	-	-
101	Dacsp1	Dacryopinax primogenitus DJM 731 SSP1 v1.0	-	-	-
102	Cryne_H99_1	Cryptococcus neoformans var. grubii H99	-	-	-
103	Trias8904	Trichosporon asahii var. asahii CBS 8904	-	-	-
104	Melame1	Melampsora americana R15-033-03 v1.0	-	-	-
104	Rhoto_IFO0880_4	Rhodosporeidium toruloides IFO0880 v4.0	-	-	-
106	Ustma2_2	Ustilago maydis 521 v2.0	-	-	-
107	Cersp1	Ceraceosorus guamensis MCA 4658 v1.0	-	-	-

Table S3. Presence / absence of NLAC, NMCO and small subunit (ss) in the analyzed fungal species. The red background highlights anomalous situations, where the small subunit (ss column) is present without NLAC genes or vice versa. Every genome containing NMCO genes also have NLAC genes.

Dataset S1 (separate excel file). Worksheet 1) Selected 20 species widely distributed throughout Basidiomycota and Ascomycota divisions to identify protein families with a single protein per species. Subsequently, these families were individually employed as protein reference databases in the final phylogeny analysis of 107 Basidiomycota species.

Worksheet 2) Enzyme sequences from each MCO group selected to carry out the filtering of initial sequences by a sequence length criterion. Number of sequences of each group chosen for sequence filtering, and their average length and Standard Deviation (SD).

Worksheet 3) Selected sequences included in the final analysis (divided by MCO groups).

Worksheet 4) Partial sequences discarded by the sequence length criterion.

Supplementary File 1 – Multiple sequence alignment of 1215 amino acid sequences of MCOs

Supplementary File 2 – Phylogenetic tree in Newick format of 1215 MCOs

Supplementary File 3 – Multiple sequence alignment of 74 selected amino acid sequences of MCOs

Supplementary File 4 – Phylogenetic tree in Newick format of 74 selected MCOs